

A new highly selective and ratiometric chromogenic sensor for Cu²⁺ detection

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Abstract : A new azo-phenol based chemosensor has been designed, synthesized and its structure is confirmed through different spectroscopic techniques. The synthesized chemosensor (HL) has shown a marked colorimetric response from light yellow to purple upon complexation with Cu²⁺ which is easily detectable through naked eyes, makes the sensor efficient one to detect Cu²⁺ and remain nonresponsive in presence of other competitive metal ions. The 1 : 1 complex formation of HL with Cu²⁺ is determined from Job's plot analysis and mass spectroscopic studies. Association constant (K_a , $8.94 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$) of HL-Cu²⁺ complex suggests HL has high affinity towards Cu²⁺.

Keywords : Azo dye, chemosensor, colorimetric detection, ratiometric, Cu²⁺ sensor, DFT calculations.

1. Introduction

Cu²⁺ is the third most abundant essential trace element after Fe³⁺ and Zn²⁺ in human body and plays a crucial role in many important physiological processes^{1,2}. Copper is being used as catalyst in a variety of biological processes and it is the cause of its requirement in every living organism³. Oxygen transportation, hormone maturation, and signal transduction etc. are the important biochemical activities of Cu²⁺⁴. For the formation of hemoglobin, red blood cells and bones of the human system, copper is treated as an essential element⁵. Besides its usefulness, copper ion at excessive concentration is very toxic. Due to its adverse effect on living beings, Cu²⁺ is also treated as a notable metal pollutant⁶. Enormous use of Cu²⁺ in our daily life makes it easily accumulate in environment which exposes to human body through contamination of food and water. The U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has set limits for copper in drinking water and food to 1.3 ppm⁷. Many severe neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's and Wilson's diseases, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, Menke's syndrome and hematological manifestations

are the effect of disorder in Cu^{II} metabolism⁸⁻¹². Thus, it is important to monitor the concentration of copper ion in environmental sample.

In this regard, an optical sensor for Cu²⁺ ion, which leads a prominent change in color is in high demand. Colorimetric sensors have been studied actively over the recent decades due to their simple, inexpensive, and rapid implementation^{13,14}. Especially, colorimetric sensors are quite promising because the change of color can easily be noticed by the naked-eye. Thus, the colorimetric sensor requires much less labor and need no equipments^{15,16}. Therefore, the development of new chemosensor for Cu²⁺ detection, especially those which exhibit selective ratiometric Cu²⁺ detection is in high demand which not only contributes to the accurate measurement of the intensities of the two absorbance peaks, but also results in a huge ratiometric value.

Herein, we have reported the synthesis and photo-physical characterizations of ONS donor thioether containing azo phenol based derivative showing a prominent ratiometric sensing towards Cu²⁺. Experimental studies reveal that the sensor exhibits a remarkable

affinity for Cu^{2+} in acetonitrile media which is associated with a color change from light yellow to pink due to the enhancement of ICT (internal charge transfer) effect.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials and methods

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was purchased from Arrora Matthey, Kolkata, India. 2-(Ethylthio)benzenamine was synthesized following the published procedure¹⁷. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used without further purification.

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer CHN-2400 elemental analyzer. HRMS mass spectra were obtained on a Waters (Xevo G2 Q-TOF) mass spectrometer. The electronic spectra were obtained on a Lambda 750 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in acetonitrile solution. IR spectra were recorded on RX-1 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the spectral range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the samples in the form of KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on a Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer in the presence of TMS as internal standard.

2.2. Synthesis

2.2.1. Synthesis of 4-chloro-2-((2-(ethylthio)phenyl)diazenyl)phenol (HL)

A solution of 2-(ethylthio)benzenamine (3.06 g, 0.02 mol) in 1 : 1 HCl (10 mL) was cooled in an ice bath. An ice cold solution of NaNO_2 (2.0 g in 10 mL water) was added under stirring. This diazotized solution was added to an ice cold solution of Na_2CO_3 (6 g in 25 mL) and 4-chlorophenol (2.56 g, 0.02 mol) with vigorous stirring. An orange-red precipitate was observed. The precipitate was filtered and washed with cold water, then dried over CaCl_2 . The product was purified further by column chromatography using silica gel (60–120 mesh) and an orange-red band was eluted by 30% (v/v) ethyl acetate-petroleum ether mixture. Yield 3.7 g (72%). The receptor HL has been characterized by elemental and mass spectral analysis along with several other spectroscopic techniques (IR, UV-Vis, NMR etc.).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of chemosensor HL : (i) $\text{Na}/\text{dry MeOH}/\text{ethyl iodide}$, (ii) $\text{NaNO}_2/\text{HCl}/4\text{-chlorophenol}$ in Na_2CO_3 ($0\text{--}5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{ClN}_2\text{OS}$ (HL) : C, 65.34; H, 5.09; N, 10.89%. Found : C, 65.13; H, 5.01; N, 10.77%; IR data (KBr, cm^{-1}) : $3434\text{ } \nu(\text{O-H})$, $1421\text{ } \nu(\text{N=N})$; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) δ (ppm) : 12.67 (1H, s), 7.95 (1H, s), 7.85 (1H, d, $J=8.0$ Hz), 7.28–7.45 (4H, m), 7.02 (1H, d, $J=8.8$ Hz), 3.04 (2H, q, $J=7.2$ Hz), 1.40 (3H, t, $J=7.3$). HRMS m/z , 280.19 (Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{OS} + \text{Na}^+$: 280.321).

2.3. Synthesis of the HL- Cu^{2+} complex

$\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was added in acetonitrile light yellow colored solution of HL and the stirring was continued for 4 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure in rotary evaporator. The residue was washed by cold water followed by n-hexane and dried in a CaCl_2 desiccator. Yield was, 0.093 g, 78%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{Cl}_2\text{CuN}_2\text{OS}$: Calcd. (%) : C, 43.03; H, 3.10; N, 7.17. Found (%) : C, 43.04; H, 3.09; N, 7.21. HRMS m/z , 413.523.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of HL- Cu^{2+} complex.

2.4. General method for UV-Vis titration

2.4.1. UV-Vis method

Stock solution of the receptor HL (10 μM) was prepared in CH_3CN at $25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The aqueous solution of the guest cations using their chloride salts in the order

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of 10^{-4} M were prepared. Solutions of various concentrations containing host and increasing concentrations of cations were prepared separately. The changes in UV-Vis spectra of receptor (10 μM) upon gradual addition of metal ion solutions were recorded.

2.4.2. Job's plot by absorbance method

For Job's plot experiment, a series of solutions containing HL (10 μM) and Cu^{2+} (10 μM) were prepared in such a manner that the sum of the total metal ion and HL volume remained constant (4 ml) in MeCN : H_2O (1 : 5, v/v) medium. Job's plots were drawn by plotting ΔA versus mole fraction of Cu^{2+} (ΔA = change of intensity of the absorption spectrum at 515 nm).

3. Results and discussion

3.3. Cation sensing studies of HL

3.3.1. UV-Vis study

Absorption study of the receptor upon gradual addition of increasing concentrations of Cu^{2+} (0–2.0 equiv.) is shown in Fig. 1. The probe shows two prominent absorbance peaks at 323 nm and 410 nm in absence of any guest analytes. After addition of Cu^{2+} a significant changes in the absorbance profile was noticed. Upon gradual addition of Cu^{2+} to the solution of HL (10 μM) in MeCN : H_2O (1 : 5, v/v) medium the absorption band at 410 nm gradually decreases and a new band appears at 515 nm which gradually increases after incremental addition of Cu^{2+} with a prominent isobestic point at 466 nm. The intensity of the new band (at 515 nm) increases appreciably with progressive addition of Cu^{2+} (up to 2 equiv.) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Changes in UV-Vis spectra of HL upon gradual addition of Cu^{2+} in MeCN : H_2O (1 : 5, v/v).

This photophysical changes leads to a prominent color change of the solution from light yellow to pink. This large red shift (105 nm) of the absorption spectra of HL is attributed due to the enhancement of ICT mechanism after complexation with guest Cu^{2+} ion. The absorbance at 515 nm exhibits a good linearity with added Cu^{2+} concentration with a very good R^2 value (Fig. 2). The detection limit of the sensor for Cu^{2+} is determined from the absorption spectral change, upon addition of Cu^{2+} to be 6.26×10^{-8} M, using the equation $\text{DL} = K \text{Sb1}/S$, where $K = 3$, Sb1 is the standard deviation of the blank solution, and S is the slope of the calibration curve. Upon incremental addition of Cu^{2+} solution, a complete reduction in the intensity at 410 nm accompanied by a ratiometric increase in intensity at 515 nm was observed which achieved saturation after the addition of a ~ 1.0 equivalent (10 μM) solution of Cu^{2+} ions (Fig. 1). The ratio of two absorption intensities (A_{410}/A_{515}) also maintained a good linear relationship with $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. The linear response curve of HL at 515 nm depending on the Cu^{2+} concentration.

The selectivity and interference are the two very important parameters to determine the novelty of any receptor. Now the sensitivity and selectivity of the probe HL towards Cu^{2+} were examined by employing different guest analytes. In addition of other guest ions (except Cu^{2+}) no noticeable change was observed in the absorbance profile (Fig. 4). Upon addition of Cu^{2+} , the absorbance of the sensor at 515 nm was

Fig. 3. Absorbance intensity ratio at A_{515}/A_{410} nm of HL depending on the Cu^{2+} concentration.

increased by 27-fold. Competition study with different metal ions (30 μM) in the solution of HL (10 μM) and Cu^{2+} (20 μM) suggesting that there is no significant interferences of other metal ions (Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Al^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , In^{3+} and Zn^{2+}) for the detection of Cu^{2+} (Fig. 5). This phenomenon indicates that the sensor can be employed conveniently for Cu^{2+} detection by simple visual inspection. So the selectivity of HL towards Cu^{2+} is thus well proven.

Fig. 4. UV-Vis spectra of HL (10 μM) in MeCN : H_2O (1 : 5, v/v) in presence of different metal ions (3 equiv.).

To understand the interaction of HL and Cu^{2+} in solution Job's plot by absorbance method was performed. Stock solution of same concentration of HL and Cu^{2+} was prepared in the order of 10 μM in

Fig. 5. Competition study using UV-Vis method, after addition of different analytes (30 μM) in the solution of HL (10 μM) in presence of Cu^{2+} (20 μM).

MeCN : H_2O (1 : 5, v/v) at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$. The UV-Vis spectrum in each case with different host-guest ratio but equal in volume was recorded. Job's plots were drawn by plotting $\Delta I \cdot X_{\text{host}}$ vs X_{host} (ΔI = change of intensity of the absorbance spectrum at 515 nm during titration and X_{host} is the mole fraction of the host in each case, respectively). From the Job's plot titration it can be concluded that the stoichiometry between HL and Cu^{2+} is 1 : 1.

The stoichiometry of the probe in the presence of Cu^{2+} is found to be 1 : 1, which is supported by the Job's plot (Fig. 6) and confirmed by HRMS experiment. The HRMS spectrum of the HL- Cu^{2+} complex gives a signal at m/z 413.5, which may be for $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})\text{Cl} + \text{Na}]^+$ species. Further to understand the stability of the HL- Cu^{2+} complex association constant calculated according to the Benesi-Hildebrand equation. K_a was calculated following the equation stated below :

$$\frac{1}{(A - A_0)} = \frac{1}{\{K_a(A_{\text{max}} - A_0) [\text{M}^{X+}] n\} + 1/[A_{\text{max}} - A_0]}$$

Here, A_0 is the absorbance of receptor in the absence of guest, A is the absorbance recorded in the presence of added guest, A_{max} is absorbance in presence of added $[\text{M}^{X+}]_{\text{max}}$ and K_a is the association constant, where $[\text{M}^{X+}]$ is $[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$. The association constant (K_a) could be determined from the slope of the straight line of the plot of $1/(A - A_0)$ against $1/[\text{Cu}^{2+}]$ and is found

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Fig. 6. Job's plot diagram of receptor for Cu^{2+} (where X_h is the mole fraction of the host and ΔI indicates the change of absorbance intensity at 515 nm).

to be $8.94 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ (Fig. 7). Thus the experiments strongly suggest that there is a strong association between the radii of Cu^{2+} and the cavity space in the probe HL, which ultimately gives rise to strong interaction between Cu^{2+} .

Fig. 7. Benesi-Hildebrand plot from absorption titration data of receptor HL (10 μM) with Cu^{2+} .

For extending the scope of experiment of synthesized probe HL, we have studied the sensing at different pH medium. The absorption intensity at 515 nm of the receptor is almost unaffected at different pH condition but in presence of Cu^{2+} ion there is large change

of absorption intensity between pH 8–11. Receptor can form stable complex with Cu^{2+} between pH 5–8. At very low pH (<3), there is a tendency to combine with proton, hence become less effective in detection of Cu^{2+} . So it is clear that our synthesized receptor can sense Cu^{2+} ion between pH 5–8.

Fig. 8. Absorbance response of HL and HL- Cu^{2+} at 515 nm (10 μM) as a function of pH.

4. Conclusion

A new azo-phenol based chemosensor has been successfully synthesized and characterized by several spectroscopic techniques. HL showed a marked colorimetric response from light yellow to purple in presence of Cu^{2+} which is easily detectable through naked eyes. Moreover, the sensor showed a selective color change in presence of Cu^{2+} and remain non responsive in presence of other competitive metal ions. The 1 : 1 host-guest complex formation of HL with Cu^{2+} is determined from Job's plot analysis and mass spectroscopic studies. Association constant (K_a , $8.94 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$) of HL- Cu^{2+} complex suggests HL has high affinity towards Cu^{2+} .

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